

Trainer User Story Analysis - RDA Minimal MD

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	Trainer looking for training resources for their own training (Tr-1)										
2	Trainer looking for existing modules to combine for a new course (Tr-2)										
3	Trainers looking for resources in a given language (Tr-3)										
4	Trainer wanting to share their materials (Tr-4)										
5	Generic Term	Description	Metadata req (Tr-1)	Useful for Extended Doc (Tr-1)	Metadata req (Tr-2)	Useful for Extended Doc (Tr-2)	Metadata req (Tr-3)	Useful for Extended Doc (Tr-3)	Metadata req (Tr-4)	Useful for Extended Doc (Tr-4)	Comment / Notes
6	title	The name of the resource.	N	N	N	N	N	N	Recmnd	Y	I was wondering. Why would we need a title, if we have for example key words...
7	abstract	A brief overview of the item (container)	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
8	abstract_data	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Recmnd	Y	either this one or the previous is helpful for reuse, but required...
9	access_cost	Choice stating whether or not there is a fee for use of the resource (Boolean).	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	I would say this is not minimum required in general.
10	author(s)	List of full name of the author(s)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
11	author.familyName	Last or family name of person(s) authoring the resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
12	author.givenName	First or given name of person(s) authoring the resource	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
13	author_org	Name of organization authoring the resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
14	contributor(s)	contributing to the resource.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	
15	contributor_orgs.name	Name of contributing organization(s)	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	
16	contributor_orgs.type	organization	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	Taxonomy)? - I like this
17	contributors.familyName	Family or last name of the contributor.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	
18	contributors.givenName	Given or first name of contributor(s)	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	

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19	name_identifier	The unique identifier for individual or organization referenced.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	
20	name_type	The name of the identifier scheme.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	
21	contributors.type	Type of contribution made by a person or organization.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	
22	contribution_date	Date of the contribution to the resource	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	
23	contribution_entity	Identification of and information about entities (i.e., people, organizations) contributing to the resource	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	
24	language_primary	Language in which the resource was originally published or made available.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Y	Y	Y	Y	see comment in M3
25	languages_secondary	Additional languages in which the resource is available, if any.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Y	Y	Y	Y	If applicable
26	keywords	Keywords or tags used to describe the resource.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	title are not available. Otherwise 'Recmnd'
27	license	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	US 6. minimal perhaps Recmnd
28	lr_type	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	N	N	Recmnd	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	US6 determines US12 here
29	target_audience	Principle users(s) for which the resource was designed.	N	Y	Recmnd	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	US2 determines US12 here
30	subject	Subject domain toward which the resource is targeted.	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	Is this the topic? Can we recommend a controlled vocab for disciplines?
31	skill_level	Target skill level in the topic being taught; example values include: beginner, intermediate, advanced.	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	
32	typical_age_range	The typical range of ages for the content's intended end user.	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	

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33	difficulty	How hard it is to work with or through the resource for the typical intended target audience (very easy, easy, medium, difficult, very difficult, knowledge-dependent)	N	N	N	Recmnd	N	N	N	Recmnd	What is difference with skill level? Only applicable when target audience is filled in.
34	published	Date of publication / broadcast.	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
35	modification_date	Date at which the educational resource was most recently published or broadcast.	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Recmnd	Y	Y	
36	version	The specific version of the resource, if declared.	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Recmnd	Y	Y	
37	publisher	The organization credited with publishing or broadcasting the resource (does not include the repository where resource is stored).	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	What is difference with author_org?
38	url	URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable.	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	This should be changed to PID, resolving URL is not persistent
39	usage_info	Text describing information about using the resource, not addressed by the license URL.	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	if applicable
40	usage_restrictions	Yes / No response to whether copyright or other restrictions apply to the use of the resource	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	we do not need this if there is a licence
41	use_rights_url	The URL where the owner specifies permissions for using the resource	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	we do not need this if there is a licence
42	learning_outcome	Descriptions of what knowledge, skills or abilities students should acquire on completion of the resource.	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	
43	citation	Preferred form of citation	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	

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44	locator.data	From DC "An unambiguous reference to the resources within a given context." Use a string that conforms to an ID system. See how FAIRsFAIR deals with this...	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	This is the PID?!
45	locator.type	Controlled vocabulary designating the persistent identifier schemes used for the resource, e.g., DOI, ARK, Handle.	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	
46	completion_time	Approximate or typical time it takes to work with or through the resource for the typical, intended target audience.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	N	N	N	Recmnd	
47	completion_status	Completion status or condition of the resource (draft, final, revised, unavailable)	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	
48	interactivity_level	Degree of interactivity characterizing the resource; refers to the degree to which the learner can influence the aspect of behavior of resource (e.g., very low, low, medium, high, very high).	Optional	It can not be required, but it is helpful, also looking for resources							
49	interactivity_type	The predominant mode of learning supported by the learning resource (i.e., active, expositive, or mixed)	Optional	Is this clear to the average trainer? What is an expositive interactive element?							
50	credential_status	Type of credentialing offered for the resource, if any.	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Y	N	N	Recmnd	Y	
51	contact	Name of person who has been asserted as the contact(s) for the resource in case of questions or follow-up by resource user.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Is this needed when there is an author?
52	email	Email address of person or organization that has been asserted as the contact for the resource.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	see above

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53	org	Name of organization that has been asserted as the contact for the resource in case of questions or follow-up by resource user.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	see above
54	media_type	From schema.org def: "Media type of resource, typically expressed using a MIME format" from IANA site & MDN reference.	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	
55	ed_frameworks.name	The name of an framework to which the resource is aligned, if any.	N	Optional	Optional	Optional	N	N	Optional	Optional	
56	ed_frameworks.nodes.description	The description of a node in an educational framework	N	Optional	Optional	Optional	N	N	Optional	Optional	
57	ed_frameworks.nodes.name	The name of a node in an established educational framework.	N	Optional	Optional	Optional	N	N	Optional	Optional	
58	ed_frameworks.nodes.url	The URL of a node in an established educational framework.	N	Optional	Optional	Optional	N	N	Optional	Optional	
59	ed_frameworks.url	The URL of an established educational framework	N	Optional	Optional	Optional	N	N	Optional	Optional	
60	alignment_type	A category of alignment between the learning resource and the framework node. (See notes for Recmnd values).									Not clear to me
61	hasPart	A sub-Training resource or externally referenced resource	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	
62	isPartOf	Course in which this resource was/will be used, or the resource in which this resource is a part (e.g., part of a book or slide-set associated with a course).	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	
63	is_based_on_url	A resource that was used in the creation of this resource (repeatable)	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	
64	resource_size	Size of the resource in bytes (uncompressed)	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	

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65	accessibility_control	Indicates input methods that are sufficient to fully control the described resource (CV list of values at https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	
66	accessibility_features	Content features of the resource, such as accessible media, alternatives and supported enhancements for accessibility (WebSchemas wiki lists possible values). Only 4 values of the entire list were available in the drupal production system; others are to be added to the CV for this field as called for.	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	
67	accessibility_hazard	A characteristic of the described resource that is physiologically dangerous to some users. (CV list of values at: https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	
68	accessibility_summary	Human readable summary of accessibility features and deficiencies	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	
69	accessibility_api	Indicates that the resource is compatible with the referenced accessibility API (CV list of values at https://www.w3.org/wiki/WebSchemas/Accessibility)	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	Optional	
70	date_created	The date on which the resource was created.	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	only needed if publication date is not the creation date
71	country_of_origin	Code for country from which resource was generated;	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	

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72	coverage	Time, culture, geography or region to which this learning object applies. The extent or scope of its content. Coverage will typically include spatial location (a place name or geographic coordinates), temporal period (a period label, date, or date range) or jurisdiction (such as a named administrative entity).	N	Recmnd	N	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	
73	mentions	Data-sets, tools, technologies, entities, other training materials in the series, etc., to which the resource makes reference. **	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	This should be repeatable?
74	context	Principal environment within which the learning & use of the resource is intended to take place, e.g., school, higher education, etc.	Optional	Recmnd	Optional	Recmnd	N	N	Optional	Recmnd	
75	purpose	The purpose of the work in the context of education.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
76	uses	Data-sets, tools, technologies, entities, etc. that are actively utilised in this resource.	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	Recmnd	This should be repeatable?
77	rating	Placeholder for comments given by users assessing the educational resource after use.	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	N	N	Optional	depends on platform, would be nice
78	ratings	If applicable, placeholder for overall ratings for the educational resource, based on a collection of reviews or ratings.	N	Optional	N	Optional	N	N	N	Optional	
79	semantic_density	Degree of conciseness; may be estimated in terms of its size, span or duration									do not understand this
80	System MD fields below:										

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81	id	System identifier for the MD record.	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	
82	md_record_id	Globally unique, persistent ID for the metadata record within the system for the resource being described.	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	
83	submitter_email	Person submitting the resource into the DMTC queue for publication.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
84	submitter_name	Email address of person submitting the resource into the DMTC queue for publication.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
85	created	The date on which the metadata record was created.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
86	creator	The login name of the person creating the MD record.	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	
87	featured_event	Course instance or event where this training resource was or will be featured. (inverse of workFeatured)	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Is this only as a system MD field. It would be nice if an event to the resource could be referenced
88											
89											
90	resource_id_label	A globally unique label that identifies the learning object.									Used by ENVRI LOM: identifier (General 1.1)
91	resource_id_scheme	Name or designator of the identification or cataloging scheme for the globally unique label (resource ID)									Used by ENVRI LOM: catalog (General 1.2)
92	resource_id_value	Value of the identifier within the identification or cataloging scheme that designates or identifies the learning object. Should be a namespace specific string.									Used by ENVRI LOM: entry (General 1.3)
93											
94	REFERENCES										
95		* Taken from https://zenodo.org/record/3903341 (ENVRI LOM profile)									
96		** Taken from https://bioschemas.org/profiles/TrainingMaterial/0.7-DRAFT-2019_11_08/									
97											